

Studies of the Catalytic Activities of some Vanadium incorporated Perovskites

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Pentavalent vanadium-incorporated perovskite oxides have been prepared, characterised and used as catalysts in the oxidation of methanol. The relative contributions of the crystal structure to the catalytic activity have also been assessed through a study of vanadium-incorporated rutile catalyst and V_2O_5 -anatase mixture. Further, an attempt has been made to explain the catalytic activities and selectivities on the basis of bond polarity and oxidation state of vanadium. Perovskites (ABO_3) containing V^{IV} in the B site were found to be quite stable.

OXIDES of the type ABO_3 with the perovskite structure are known for their catalytic activity in the fields of automobile exhaust emission control and photoelectrolysis¹⁻⁴. The present paper pertains to the preparation, characterisation and catalytic use of pentavalent vanadium-containing perovskites.

Experimental

The catalysts were prepared by the total impregnation method⁵. Perovskite type catalysts were labelled STV-10, STV-20, STV-25 and STV-29, where S indicates strontium, T indicates titanium and V denotes vanadium. Numerals at the end of the symbols indicate the atomic percentages of the vanadium component in the samples. Binary oxide mixtures of titanium and vanadium were prepared⁶ in two series: low temperature preparations and high temperature preparations, and they were labelled AVY and RVB, respectively. AVY (anatase-vanadium-yellow) samples were yellow in colour and contained anatase form of TiO_2 . RVB (rutile-vanadium-black) samples were black in colour and contained rutile form of TiO_2 . Lanthanum and lithium-incorporated $SrTiO_3$ were prepared by impregnation method starting from $SrTiO_3$.

X-Ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the powdered samples were recorded using CuK_{α} radiation with Ni filter in a Dron-1 unit. Pycnometric densities were determined using CCl_4 as the liquid and $SrTiO_3$ as the standard. Infrared spectra were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the range $625-2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Chemical analysis was carried out following the method of Bielenski⁷. Surface area measurements were made by the BET method⁸ using nitrogen as adsorbate. Catalytic vapour phase oxidation of methanol was carried out in a flow reactor. Details of the experiment are given in a previous paper⁹.

Results and Discussion

XRD patterns of STV-10, STV-20 and STV-25 could all be indexed using the Hull-Davey chart¹⁰ to a tetragonally distorted perovskite, the lattice parameters of which are presented in Table 1. XRD pattern of STV-29 was identical with that of $SrTiO_3$. Comparison of pycnometric densities with those calculated on the basis of the lattice parameters obtained from XRD indicated the presence of vacancies in the lattices of STV samples and in La-containing samples, and the presence of interstitialcy in Li-containing samples. XRD patterns of AVY and RVB samples broadly agreed with those of the same samples prepared by previous workers¹¹.

TABLE 1—LATTICE PARAMETERS OF STV CATALYSTS

Sample code	c Å	a Å	c/a
STV-10	7.97	7.80	1.022
STV-20	8.14	7.78	1.055
STV-25	8.21	7.70	1.066
STV-29	3.91	3.91	1.000

Infrared spectra of AVY-10 and RVB-10 showed a broad band at 1020 cm^{-1} which was absent in RVB-4 and all STV samples. This band can be ascribed to $V=O$ double bond¹².

Chemical analysis revealed the presence of V^{IV} ions in RVB samples. Neither AVY nor STV series contained any V^{IV} in concentrations detectable through chemical analysis.

Surface area values of AVY samples were found to be around $9\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$. RVB and STV samples had low surface area, around $1.5\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$.

The results of catalytic experiments are given in Tables 2-4. The use of aqueous methanol in

place of pure methanol as feed resulted in a drastic decrease in conversion and an increase in selectivity (Table 3). Use of pyridine-chemisorbed STV-20 showed a huge decrease in both conversion and selectivity.

TABLE 2—CATALYTIC ACTIVITIES OF SrTiO₃, La-SUBSTITUTED SrTiO₃ AND Li-SUBSTITUTED SrTiO₃

Sample	C %	S %	Conditions W/F
SrTiO ₃	4.4	79.6	15.4
La _{0.07} -doped SrTiO ₃	6.7	46.8	15.4
4% Li-incorporated SrTiO ₃	0.94	100	11.58

$$\text{Percentage conversion (C)} = \frac{\text{Moles of methanol converted}}{\text{Moles of methanol fed}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Percentage selectivity (S)} = \frac{\text{Moles of methanol converted to HCHO}}{\text{Moles of methanol converted to HCHO and CO}_2} \times 100$$

$$W/F = \frac{\text{Weight of catalyst (g)}}{\text{Feed rate of methanol (mol h}^{-1}\text{)}}$$

TABLE 3—CATALYTIC ACTIVITIES AND SELECTIVITIES OF SOME STV SAMPLES UNDER PRODUCT INHIBITION/PYRIDINE ADSORPTION

Sample	C %	S %	A.C.A.	A.C.Y.	Conditions
STV-20	7.8	89.0	0.89	0.36	50% aq. methanol (product) inhibition
STV-25	10.5	89.0	0.42	0.38	same as above
STV-30	5.3	57.6	0.28	0.15	Pyridine-treated catalyst
STV-20	2.5	54.8	0.12	0.07	Methanol containing one mole % pyridine as feed

$$\text{A.C.A.} = \frac{\text{Percent conversion}}{\text{Atomic \% of V in catalyst}} \times 100$$

$$\text{A.C.Y.} = \frac{\text{Percent yield of formaldehyde}}{\text{Atomic \% of V in catalyst}} \times 100$$

TABLE 4—CATALYTIC ACTIVITY OF AVY, RVB AND STV SAMPLES

Weight of catalyst = 1 g, W/F (g h mol⁻¹) = 11.58

Sample	Conversion %	Selectivity %	ACA	AOY
AVY-10	24.1	77.2	2.41	1.86
AVY-20	32.3	88.2	1.61	1.43
AVY-25	36.3	89.7	1.45	1.30
AVY-29	38.5	91.2	1.29	1.17
RVB-4	11.8	81.9	2.90	2.46
RVB-10	16.77	86.4	1.68	1.45
RVB-20	20.3	83.5	1.03	0.85
RVB-25	23.5	83.4	0.94	0.78
RVB-29	29.2	86.0	0.97	0.84
STV-4	6.5	64.4	1.63	1.06
STV-10	9.17	81.7	0.92	0.75
STV-20	13.99	71.25	0.70	0.50
STV-25	17.86	67.56	0.71	0.48
STV-29	10.26	79.25	0.34	0.27

Continuous runs for 6 h showed that the activity of AVY-20 decreased considerably at the end of the time period. RVB-20 and STV-20 retained their steady state activity to a very large extent for the same period. Analysis of the spent catalysts by chemical and X-ray studies revealed a good degree of reduction on AVY-20 surface. RVB-20 showed much less reduction while STV showed no reduction at all.

Conversion over TiO₂ (the matrix in AVY and RVB) had been found to be very low for this reaction by earlier workers¹³. SrTiO₃ (the matrix in STV) has been found in the present work to be practically inactive. Inappreciable low activity of the Li-incorporated samples (Table 2) showed the Ti^{III} ions to be catalytically inactive. Thus the activities of the vanadium-containing catalysts are exclusively due to the presence of the vanadium ions.

Among the three series, the trend in catalytic activity was AVY > RVB > STV. The V=O bond is perhaps labile in AVY as is evidenced by ir spectra, $\nu_{V=O}$ being 1020 cm⁻¹, whilst the double bonds are either not labile or not so numerous in RVB samples⁹. Perovskite (ABO₃) structure does not provide any scope for the formation of B=O bonds. As regards selectivity, all AVY samples except AVY-10 had higher values than the corresponding RVB and STV samples. At the 10 atomic % concentration, the sequences becomes AVY > STV > RVB. The V^{IV} ions which are the active centres in vanadium catalysts¹⁴ are present in larger concentrations in RVB than in AVY or STV, as revealed by chemical analysis. In RVB, the V^{IV} ions originate both from V^{IV}-substituted rutile and ion-deficient V₂O₅, whilst these ions in the other two series stem from ion-deficient V₂O₅ or V-substituted perovskite only. The selectivity pattern showed (Table 4) that V^{IV} in a rutile matrix was more selective than in a perovskite matrix.

Among the STV catalysts the tetragonality (*c/a* ratio) gradually increases from STV-10 through STV-20 to STV-25 and reverts to the value of unity at STV-29 (Table 1). In perovskite oxides the transition metal ions are situated at sufficiently large distances from each other so that a gas molecule interacts with a single site. With an increase in the *c/a* ratio the single point adsorption occurs with greater facility¹⁵. This is a likely reason for the increase in conversion on passing from STV-10 to STV-25 (Table 4). Ordering of B ions in STV-25 (as suggested by X-ray studies) involves positioning of vanadium ions at the end of the body diagonal of the perovskite lattice. Maximum separation of active sites is thus achieved. In STV-29, vanadium ions are closer than in STV-25 accounting for the lower activity of the former. Selectivity reaches a minimum at 25 atomic % V (Table 4). Selectivity to formaldehyde formation over oxide catalysts have often been linked to polarity of the B—O bond in the catalysts¹⁶. Obviously an interplay of the polarities of the V^V—O, Ti^{IV}—O and Sr—O bonds brings

about the observed trend in selectivity. The absence of any pronounced decrease in atomic catalytic yield (A.C.Y.) from STV-20 to STV-29 defies explanation. It is possible that methanol adsorption which is a prelude to formaldehyde formation is not affected by the increase in the extent of dispersion of vanadium in the catalyst. Both A.C.A. (atomic catalytic activity) and A.C.Y. decrease due to product inhibition (Table 3). Formation of HCHO is less affected than CO₂ formation. Water being more basic than methanol, competitively gets adsorbed on weaker acidic sites not suitable for methanol adsorption¹⁷. This hydroxylation of the surface probably blocks oxygen adsorption which is the most important precursor to deep oxidation.

The decrease in activity observed with the pyridine-adsorbed sample suggests that acidic centres are required for formaldehyde formation or for CO₂ formation or for both. Yield of HCHO has been decreased to a larger extent than yield of CO₂ (Tables 3 and 4). Thus adsorption of methanol on coordinately unsaturated metal ions which is responsible for HCHO formation is impeded by pyridine adsorption.

All the STV catalysts and lanthanum-substituted SrTiO₃ possess A-site vacancies as revealed by density measurements and XRD patterns. The lanthanum compound which contains only catalytically inactive ions was more active but less selective than SrTiO₃ (Table 2). Thus it appears that A-site possesses activity only when vacant⁴. A-site vacancies owe their activity to a crystallographic shear process¹⁸. That STV-20 and RVB-4 could be used continuously for 6 h without the necessity for reoxidation by intermittent current of air, shows

the stability of the vanadium ions in a perovskite lattice or in a rutile lattice.

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